

Effect of azolla on insect predators

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Azolla water fern floats on paddy water and creates in the rice field ecosystem an additional niche that influences insect predators living on or in the water. Net samples including applied and naturally occurring azolla, paddy water, and bottom mud were taken 12 times from Oct to Dec 1982 from transplanted rice fields on the IRRI experimental farm. More predators were counted in samples taken from fields with applied azolla (303) than from other fields (191) (see table).

The water-surface inhabiting species most favored by azolla were rice hopper predators *Microvelia douglasi atrolineata* (Bergroth) [Veliidae], *Paraplea sobrina* (Stål) [Pleidae], and *Lycosa pseudoannulata* (Boes. et Str.) [Lycosidae]. The rice bund-inhabiting spiders *Pardosa birmanica* Simon, *Arctosa janetscheki* Buchar, and *Hippasa rimandoi* Baxion [Lycosidae] moved into the azolla. Among the subsurface species, azolla favored notonectid backswimmers, pleid water bugs, water treaders, and coenagrionid damselfly naiads. Surface-dwelling Gerrid water striders and the libellulid dragonfly preferred open water. Other groups of insect predators either were unaffected by azolla or were too few to allow comparisons.

Effect of azolla on rice insect predator populations in a rice field, IRRI farm, 6 Oct to 16 Dec 1982.

	Predators (no./family) ^a																Total				
	Hemiptera								Coleoptera				Odonata		Araneae						
	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N	O	P		Q	R	S	T
With azolla	57	38	28	26	4	2	2	1	24	18	14	11	8	6	17	0	42	2	1	2	303
Without azolla	31	20	16	10	3	2	13	2	18	20	9	10	4	6	2	7	16	1	0	1	191

^aTotal of 12 net samples. A = Veliidae, B = Pleidae, C = Notonectidae, D = Mesoveliidae, E = Ochteridae, F = Nepidae, G = Gerridae, H = Belostomatidae, I = Dytiscidae, J = Hydrophilidae, K = Hydracarinae, L = Gyrinidae, M = Carabidae, N = Staphylinidae, O = Coenagrionidae, P = Libellulidae, Q = Lycosidae, R = Theridiosomatidae, S = Theridiidae, and T = Tetragnathidae.

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